

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Members of the eDNAqua-Plan Consortium

Version 1 – last updated 17-09-2025

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring

Members of the eDNAqua-Plan Consortium

ASSOCIACAO BIOPOLIS (BIOPOLIS)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Pedro	Beja	pbeja@cibio.up.pt	0000-0001-8164-0760
Manuel	Lopes-Lima	mlopeslima@cibio.up.pt	0000-0002-2761-7962
Camila	Babo	camila.babo@cibio.up.pt	0009-0004-7916-9833
Filipa	Martins	filipamsmartins@cibio.up.pt	0000-0003-4191-5031
Joana	Verissimo	j_verissimo@cibio.up.pt	0000-0002-8721-9376

EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY (EMBL)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Josephine	Burgin	burgin@ebi.ac.uk	0000-0002-9818-1094
Guy	Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	0000-0001-7954-7057
Jonny	Micklewright	grants@ebi.ac.uk	
Woollard	Peter	woollard@ebi.ac.uk	0000-0002-7654-6902

EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM (EMBRIC-ERIC)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Christina	Pavloudi	christina.pavloudi@embric.eu	0000-0001-5106-6067
Nicolas	Pade	nicolas.pade@embric.eu	0000-0003-2733-9752

EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK (EV ILVO)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Sofie	Derycke	sofie.derycke@ilvo.vlaanderen.be	0000-0003-3763-6187

DIETHNES PANEPISTIMIO ELLADOS (IHU)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Ioannis	Kavakiotis	ikavakiotis@gmail.com	0000-0003-4240-3636
Spiros	Papakostas	spapakostas@ihu.edu.gr	0000-0002-5563-0048

INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT (INRAE)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Isabelle	Domaizon	isabelle.domaizon@inrae.fr	0000-0001-9785-3082
Frédéric	Rimet	frederic.rimet@inrae.fr	0000-0002-5514-869X
Marion	Roques	marion.roques@inrae.fr	

Marine	Vautier	marine.vautier@inrae.fr	0000-0001-5830-0047
--------	---------	-------------------------	---------------------

E-SCIENCE EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH (Lifewatch ERIC)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Christos	Arvanitidis	ceo@lifewatch.eu	0000-0002-6924-5255
Cristina	Huertas Olivares	cristina.huertas@lifewatch.eu	0000-0003-2660-4649

NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING (NIVA)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Paul Ragnar	Berg	paul.berg@niva.no	0000-0002-4974-8509
Elianne	Egge	elianne.egge@niva.no	0000-0001-5790-6426

SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES (SLU)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Maria	Kahlert	aria.kahlert@slu.se	0000-0001-9643-4281

SEASCAPE BELGIUM (SSBE)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Tim	Collart	tim.collart@seascapebelgium.be	0000-0003-1562-3115
Carlijn	Koole	carlijn.koole@seascapebelgium.be	0009-0004-4052-5829
Oonagh	McMeel	oonagh.mcmeel@seascapebelgium.be	0000-0002-2221-6019

SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (SU)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Fabrice	Not	fabrice.not@sb-roscoff.fr	0000-0002-9342-195X
Ian	Probert	probert@sb-roscoff.fr	0000-0002-1643-1759

SUOMEN YMPARISTOKESKUS (SYKE)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Tiina	Laamanen	tiina.laamanen@syke.fi	0000-0003-2095-9916
Kristian	Meissner	kristian.meissner@syke.fi	0000-0001-6316-8554
Veera	Norros	veera.norros@syke.fi	0000-0002-7481-0693
Satu	Soini	satu.soini@syke.fi	0009-0003-3343-3558

UNIVERSITAET DUISBURG-ESSEN (UDE)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Arne	Beermann	arne.beermann@uni-due.de	0000-0003-0403-0322
Sandra	Kramm	sandra.kramm@uni-due.de	
Florian	Leese	florian.leese@uni-due.de	0000-0002-5465-913X

UNIVERSITY OF OSLO (UIO)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Micah	Dunthorn	micah.dunthorn@nhm.uio.no	0000-0003-1376-4109

UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO (UMINHO)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
M. Pilar	Cabezas Rodriguez	pilarcabezas@bio.uminho.pt	0000-0003-3026-9281
Filipe	Costa	fcosta@bio.uminho.pt	0000-0002-3064-0469
Sofia	Duarte	sduarte@bio.uminho.pt	0000-0002-0181-0676
Sofia	Machado	smachado@bio.uminho.pt	0000-0001-5170-0101
Jorge	Moutinho	jorge.er.moutinho@gmail.com	0000-0002-3201-4672
Pedro	Soares	pedrosoares@bio.uminho.pt	0000-0002-2807-690X

UNITED NATIONS EDUCATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL ORGANIZATION (UNESCO)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Ward	Appeltans	w.appeltans@unesco.org	0000-0002-3237-4547
Saara	Saara Suominen	s.suominen@unesco.org	0000-0001-9401-8460
Emilie	Boulanger	e.boulanger@unesco.org	0000-0002-6446-7342

UNIwersytet Łódzki (UniLodz)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Michał	Grabowski	michal.grabowski@biol.uni.lodz.pl	0000-0002-4551-3454
Karolina	Bacela-Spychalska	karolina.bacela@biol.uni.lodz.pl	0000-0003-4498-5107
Dawid	Krawczyk	dawid.krawczyk@biol.uni.lodz.pl	0000-0002-5276-7436
Tomasz	Rewicz	tomasz.rewicz@biol.uni.lodz.pl	0000-0002-2085-4973
Michał	Seweryn	michal.seweryn@biol.uni.lodz.pl	0000-0002-9090-3435

UNIVERSITAT DE VALENCIA (UVEG)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Antonio	Camacho	antonio.camacho@uv.es	0000-0003-0841-2010
Ferran	Palero	Ferran.Palero@uv.es	0000-0002-0343-8329
Antonio	Picazo	antonio.picazo-mozo@uv.es	0000-0002-7572-9686

VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE (VLIZ)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Katrina	Exter	katrina.exter@vliz.be	0000-0002-5911-1536
Pascal I.	Hablützel	pascal.hablutzel@vliz.be	0000-0002-6739-4994

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (WU)

First name	Last name	Email	ORCID
Auriel	Sumner-Hempel	auriel.sumner-hempel@wur.nl	0000-0001-5519-0532
Reindert	Nijland	reindert.nijland@wur.nl	0000-0003-0049-3768

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

